

Cultural identity of Kazakhstan: a historico-philosophical analysis

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the philosophical interpretation of Kazakhstan's cultural identity through the lens of historical and cultural development. The authors critically examine the traditional historiographical model that traces the beginning of Kazakhstan's history to the Stone Age, arguing for a more critical approach to such chronology, particularly given the climatic aridization that occurred in the region at the turn of the second to first millennium BCE. The philosophical analysis presented here reconsiders the nomadic lifestyle as a form of productive rather than appropriative economy. This rethinking allows for the recognition of early cultural coherence and an intrinsic logic in the historical development of the region. It is emphasized that the cultural identity of the Kazakh people was formed within the broader Turkic world, which is characterized by a unified way of life and common ethnocultural foundations. Historical evidence suggests that the peoples inhabiting the territory of present-day Kazakhstan since ancient times shared similar lifestyles, cultural identities, and, presumably, ethnic composition – all being of Turkic origin.

Special attention is given to the transformation of ethnocultural identity under colonial and Soviet influence, during which the cultural self-identification of Kazakhs and other ethnic groups was subjected to external political and cultural pressures. Today, Kazakhstan, having gained sovereignty, faces the challenge of being a multiethnic and multicultural – and thus multi-identity state. The primary task is to support and enhance the harmonious character of this condition.

Keywords: philosophy of cultural identity, the ethnonym “Kazakh”, sedentarism, climate aridization, nomadism

Introduction

The issue of cultural identity in any nation-state is of critical importance, both for those in governance and for its citizens. A deep understanding of the cultural distinctiveness of Kazakhs and all other ethnic groups in Kazakhstan plays a pivotal role in contemporary processes of self-identification and in shaping perspectives on global transformations.

Modern philosophical and cultural approaches not only enable an analysis of the ethnophilosophical foundations of Kazakh worldviews – shaped by a historical nomadic heritage – but also demonstrate how this heritage remains a vital component of the nation's cultural core today. Such an analysis helps uncover the underlying mechanisms shaping cultural identity and outlines potential pathways for its future development.

This is especially relevant in a state that, for various historical reasons, has evolved into a multiethnic and multicultural society. This raises the question of whether such diversity has always existed or whether it emerged at a specific point in history and under what conditions. Only by addressing this can we begin to explore how to harmonize interethnic and intercultural relations without infringing upon the rights of individual ethnic groups and cultures. The present article addresses only the first part of this complex issue.

Methodology

The methodological foundation of this research is grounded in the principle of concrete historicism, or the cultural-historical approach. This perspective regards cultural identity as a phenomenon shaped by unique historical conditions, sociocultural transformations, and the metaphysical foundations of a people's existence. Identity, in this context, is not seen as an abstract or universal given, but as a dynamic, living reality embedded in the specific historical fate of Kazakhstani society.

The principle of concrete historicism enables the investigation of identity through the lens of cultural codes accumulated in collective consciousness and helps reveal the internal logic of their evolution. Cultural distinctiveness is therefore not presented as a fixed set of traits but as the result of a dialectical process wherein tradition engages in dialogue with modernity, and the local interacts with the global. The philosophical analysis applies fundamental categories of classical dialectics – identity and difference, essence and appearance, content and form. The category of identity highlights stable elements of cultural identity that persist over time, while the category of difference captures shifts influenced by internal and external forces. The content-form pair allows for tracing how internal value systems, worldviews, and mental structures of the peoples of Kazakhstan are expressed in evolving cultural and social forms. The essence-appearance dichotomy ensures analytical depth by distinguishing between superficial manifestations of identity and its deeper structure rooted in historical consciousness.

Thus, this philosophical methodology moves beyond empirical description and approaches the ontological and axiological foundations of cultural identity, understood as a multidimensional and evolving process.

Cultural Identity in the Ancient History of Kazakhstan

Every nation emerges at a certain point in time, exists for a while, and eventually disappears from history due to various reasons and external influences. It may merge with another nation, be destroyed, or dispersed as a result of wars or natural disasters. Migration and the resettlement of peoples is another historical phenomenon. While a territory may remain geographically stable, many different peoples may inhabit it over time. This does not imply that the history of the current inhabitants, who possess a specific ethnonym, should be traced back to the creation of the world. Nevertheless, many textbooks on the history of Kazakhstan begin this narrative from the Stone Age, followed by the Bronze and Iron Ages. For instance, G. Kan writes: “Traces of human presence on the territory of Kazakhstan, such as stone tools – hand axes, scrapers, and pointed implements date back to the Lower Paleolithic (approximately 1 million years ago)” (Kan G. V. 2011). But can we assert that those early humans living in Kazakhstan during the Lower Paleolithic have a direct connection to modern Kazakhs? And when, in fact, did the Kazakhs emerge?

Shakarim Kudaiberdiuly relied on the Bible for genealogical insights. He wrote: “Noah had three sons – Shem, Ham, and Japheth. The Turkic people descended from Japheth” (Shakarim Kudaiberdyuli 1990: 11). In a more elaborate version, he added: “The Kazakhs trace their lineage to Japheth, son of the prophet Noah, and to the people known as Tuku (in Chinese), that is, the Turks. The word Turk means

'helmet'. Subsequently, this Turkic people came to be called the Huns. Najip Gasymbek asserts that this name derives from the river Orkhon. In later centuries, the Turks were known by many different names, but we are of the Uyghur branch. All known genealogies interpret the word 'Uyghur' as meaning 'united' or 'those who joined together' (Shakarim Kudaiberdyuli 1990: 41). Yet, as a conscientious thinker, Shakarim acknowledged: "There exists no genealogy that can consistently trace all generations from the prophet Adam to the present day. Even from Az-Zhanibek to the modern era, the records of our ancestors are a mixture of accurate data and clearly mythical narratives" (Shakarim Kudaiberdyuli 1990: 42).

What may be excusable for Shakarim, a man of his time, cannot be excused in the works of some contemporary authors writing about the history of Kazakhs and Kazakhstan. Those who narrate history in the same manner as Shakarim do not adhere to scientific principles – foremost among them, objectivity – but instead engage in deliberate myth-making aimed at artificially antiquating Kazakh origins. One such example is Zh. Artykbayev, who, echoing Shakarim's words, claims that "Alasha Khan, 'the first khan of the Kazakhs', was a contemporary of the prophet Noah and his son Japheth" (Artykbaev 2006: 4). "Our ancestors," he continues, "created the world's first nomadic civilization, in perfect harmony with the surrounding natural world. In this environment, the idea of the state emerged, and the energy of this idea later influenced both near and distant neighbors" (Orlova 2010). Of course, such mythologizing would not have been accepted if not for the fact that Soviet historical scholarship – including that of Kazakhstan — had many honest and responsible scholars.

As noted by the prominent Kazakhstani nomadologist N. Masanov, the motivation behind such works stems from a desire "to push the origins of Kazakh society, statehood, and ethnogenesis as far back as possible, and to excessively expand the spatiotemporal scope of ds of historical deepening. In some cases, these tendencies faded sooner; in others, they persisted longer. Kazakhstan, as a newly sovereign state, was no exception.

Human history begins with loosely organized groups – more akin to animal herds – that led a nomadic, foraging lifestyle. This corresponds to what is termed a "subsistence economy, based primarily on hunting, gathering, and, to some extent, fishing – representing the most ancient stage of economic and cultural development" (Andrianov 1989: 148). At this stage, appropriation was the dominant mode of subsistence. However, as L. Fainberg rightly notes, among the vast diversity of early primitive cultures, only those that followed the main evolutionary path – from the early Paleolithic to the late Paleolithic, then to the Mesolithic and Neolithic – can be considered "typical" with increasing influence arising from cultural interrelations (Fainberg 1983:137). Through both peaceful and conflictual interactions, cultures developed mutual awareness and began to form identity distinctions. Initially, intercultural identities emerged through the "us-them" dichotomy, and only later did intracultural identities become fixed. Similarly, the first exchanges of goods, tools, knowledge, and customs occurred between communities, not within them.

As forms of activity and tools evolved, and as blood kinship-based social structures matured, humanity gradually transitioned from a nomadic to a semi-sedentary lifestyle. Temporary settlements began to appear – defined by their relative permanence and presence of residential and work structures (Andrianov 1683: 144). *These settlements were generally located near water sources.*

The shift from subsistence-based to productive economies occurred during what is known as the Neolithic Revolution. This marked a transition from gathering and hunting to agriculture and animal husbandry. The primary means of subsistence now became cultivated plants and domesticated animals. The development of agriculture required specialized knowledge and skills, giving rise to craftsmanship – a separate field focused on producing tools and household items. Members of a single community began to acquire unique identities distinguishing them from one another. These two activities – agriculture and craftsmanship – necessitated prolonged attachment to a specific territory. Temporary settlements thus evolved into permanent ones, marking the transition to sedentism. B. Andrianov notes: "The general line of human development, including its culture and sedentary forms, is tied to the emergence and expansion of productive economies" (Andrianov 1683): 115). Sedentism displaced the nomadic way of life. Initially, settlements were disorganized and chaotic. However, as material production and spiritual culture developed, they brought structure and order. Streets and squares appeared in villages. A well-organized settlement whose inhabitants specialized in agriculture and sedentary livestock breeding came to be defined as a village. As archaic societies transitioned to post-archaic forms, cities emerged. These cities became centers of craftsmanship and local governance. The rise of cities is closely linked to the emergence of political organization – the state. Governmental institutions were concentrated in urban centers. According to Max Weber, from an economic perspective, a city is a settlement primarily based on crafts and trade: "It should be considered typical," he writes, "that a city, emerging as a formation distinct from rural settlements, becomes the seat of the lord or prince, as well as the site of a marketplace and the location of two economic centers – the oikos and the market..." (Veber M. Gorod 1994: 309–310). A state, by definition, is characterized by a specific territory encompassing numerous villages and towns. The city where the main governmental bodies are located is referred to as the capital. This was the path taken by the majority of the world's population.

Nomadism as a Cultural and Historical Phenomenon

Nomadism refers to a way of life in which people move continuously or periodically from one place to another without permanent housing. Such people are known as nomads.

Key features of nomadism he main characteristics of nomadism include the absence of a fixed place of residence and a life "on the move": relocation depends on seasons, resources, or work. It can be traditional (such as pastoralism or hunting) or modern (such as digital nomadism). Types of nomadism: Traditional nomadism is characteristic of both ancient and contemporary nomadic peoples. People migrate in search of pastures for livestock, water, or food. Examples include Mongols, Kazakhs, and Bedouins. Modern nomadism (digital nomadism) refers to people who work remotely and live in various countries or cities without settling down. Their "office" is a laptop and internet connection, and their home is any place on the map. This lifestyle is popular among freelancers, IT specialists, and travelers.

Interesting facts: The word "nomadism" derives from the Greek nomás, meaning "wandering". It is not only a lifestyle but also a philosophy: freedom, mobility, and minimal attachment. In the 21st century, it has become a trend – people strive for freedom from the "office cage" and routine.

However, alongside the dominant trajectory of humankind toward sedentarism, there exist societies that maintain a *nomadic* way of life. How is this possible? In scholarly discourse, nomadism is understood as "forms of economy and everyday life based on extensive pastoralism (including reindeer herding) with seasonal movement of people and livestock herds. Pastoralism in nomadic conditions provided nomads with meat and dairy products, raw materials for clothing and shelter. While pastoralism was the foundation of nomadic

activity, it was supplemented to varying degrees by hunting, non-sedentary primitive agriculture, crafts, and other trades. There have never been 'pure' nomads for whom pastoralism was the only form of economic activity" (Vajnshtejn 1989:72).

For a long time, literature was dominated by a biased attitude toward nomadism and the culture it produced. This was due to the glorification of settled lifestyles and a lack of understanding of the origins of nomadism. Development criteria suitable for the study of sedentary cultures were unjustifiably applied to nomadic ones, and in light of these criteria, the latter appeared underdeveloped. Researchers failed to understand that "generally accepted criteria for the level of civilizational development – the presence of writing, crafts, etc., which help assess urban culture are fundamentally inapplicable to evaluating the level of culture achieved by various societies of non-sedentary herders" (Areshyan 1989: 21). Only gradually did understanding begin to emerge. A renowned specialist on nomadism, Professor of Anthropology at the University of Wisconsin, Anatoly Khazanov, warns his colleagues that it is time to abandon myths about nomads and attempt to objectively understand the essence and causes of nomadism. He writes that if nomadism is approached as a specialized pastoral economy and evaluated as more than just one form of economic adaptation in the evolution of human history, then it is necessary to rid oneself of "the pressure of self-evaluations" and assumptions originating from other societies and developmental paths (Hazanov A. M. 2000: 68). In other words, it is necessary to adopt an objective that is, truly scientific – position and to study the phenomenon of nomadism "without anger and bias" as the saying goes. The first thing to consider, Khazanov notes, is not to confuse wandering and nomadic lifestyles. The first is characterized by a subsistence economy, while the second is productive. "...Therefore, their mobility is caused by different reasons and takes on different forms" (Hazanov A. M. 2000: 83).

According to Khazanov's generalized description of nomadism, the most important features of nomadic pastoralism that define its economic nature are as follows: pastoralism, being the dominant form of economic activity, has an extensive character associated with year-round grazing on natural pastures without stabling; seasonal mobility within or between designated grazing territories (unlike large-scale migrations); the participation of the entire or majority of the population in migrations (unlike shepherding or transhumant pastoralism); and a subsistence economy aimed primarily at meeting immediate needs (unlike modern capitalist ranching or dairy farming) (Hazanov A. M. 2000: 84–85). It appears that Khazanov correctly identified the main characteristics of the nomadic economy.

It is now generally established that the nomadic way of life did not emerge as a continuation of the foraging lifestyle at a more advanced level. The Neolithic Revolution led to the transition to a sedentary way of life, which in turn gave rise to a productive economy in the form of agriculture and/or settled animal husbandry. Consequently, the nomadic lifestyle may have replaced *not* the foraging, *but* the sedentary way of life. The reason behind this transition, according to the majority of scholars, was a rapid by historical standards – change in climate that made settled life impossible. In the Eurasian space, this change was marked by climate *aridization*. As noted by Khazanov, "the desiccation of the climate was the final push that compelled herders to abandon agriculture completely and fully adopt nomadism" (Hazanov A. M. 2000: 187).

Nomadism emerged at the turn of the second to first millennium BCE as a result of a sharp climatic shift. In the territory of Kazakhstan, this change was, as mentioned above, aridization. As N. Masanov rightly observed, nomads developed "one of the most rational methods in the pre-industrial period for utilizing and managing the scarce resources of arid regions...", and no alternative to nomadism as a strategy for nature use has been found, even in such developed and wealthy countries as Saudi Arabia, the UAE, Kuwait, and others (Masanov 1995: 42). The economic life of nomads, their lifestyle, and other sociocultural parameters depended on environmental and climatic conditions and their seasonal fluctuations, the availability of water sources, and the natural constraints of the landscape. The development of this type of economy could only be extensive, and, in the end, a relatively dynamic balance was formed between pasture resources, herd sizes, and the overall population of nomads. Naturally, the nomads themselves understood this well.

The peoples inhabiting the arid steppe were surrounded by sedentary cultures from both the north and the south. There was constant interaction between the sedentary peoples and the nomads of the arid zone, which, apart from military clashes, was beneficial to both sides (see Khlopin 1987). There was always an exchange not only of material goods and everyday items but also of elements of spiritual culture. These contacts contributed to mutual recognition and understanding of identity, which facilitated closer cooperation. (Tuyakbaeva B.T., Proskurin A.N. 1989). The famous Silk Road passed through nomadic territories, and cities emerged at suitable locations along the route, which had a highly positive effect on the relations between nomads and representatives of sedentary cultures (Akhmetzhanov, Alimzhanova 2019). In other words, it can be said that these nomads, the ancestors of the Kazakhs and the Kazakhs themselves, were in a rather advantageous position.

A. J. Toynbee, influenced by sedentary-centrism, classified nomadism as a "retarded civilization" and believed it arose "as a response to the challenge of the natural environment..." (Tojnbi A. 2021: 181). He wrote that, in responding to the harsh challenge of Nature, people "adapted to live in conditions where neither farmers nor hunters could survive. Only the herder could master the arid steppe, but in order to survive and thrive, the nomadic herder had to constantly improve and develop new skills, as well as particular moral and intellectual qualities" (Tojnbi A. 2021:185). Here, Toynbee reasons as a representative of the West, confident that progress is on his side. In reality, however, it is not a matter of *delay* but rather of the *development* of a specific survival strategy in a region that, under conditions of aridization, is virtually uninhabitable.

Poststructuralist philosophers Gilles Deleuze and Félix Guattari authored a "Treatise on Nomadology". How do these authors interpret nomadism? According to them, the key distinction between nomadism and sedentarism lies in the organization of space in which these forms of life unfold. Deleuze and Guattari refer to nomadic space as "smooth" space. "Smooth space," they write, "does not have channels or paths. It is a heterogeneous field corresponding to a specific type of multiplicity – decentralized, rhizomatic multiplicities that do not differentiate the space they occupy. This space can be exploited only by traversing it" (Deleuze J., Guattari F. 1992: 185). This space does not possess a center or periphery in either real or ideal (value-based) terms. A center in this case, if perceived at all, may be defined only subjectively, as the current location of the nomad. This space, of course, is significantly more attached to the landscape, as is all nomadic culture in general... yet in its essence, it is just as "beyond nature" as the space of sedentary culture. They write that the nomad has a territory, moving along stable routes and sequentially visiting key points, such as water sources, resting places, and gathering areas. However, it is important to understand what is primary and what is secondary in the life of the nomad. First, although the route is defined by these points, the points themselves are subordinate to the route, unlike sedentary people, for whom such points determine the direction of movement. The nomad's path lies between these points, but the transition itself acquires intrinsic meaning and a sense of internal completeness. The life of a nomad is a constant "in-between," a kind of intermezzo. Second, although nomads may move along roads, these are not the roads as perceived by sedentary peoples. For the sedentary, a road is a means of organizing enclosed space, which is divided into segments interconnected by paths. In contrast, the nomad's path is the opposite of a road: it does not connect but rather

separates people and animals in an open, unbounded, and unstructured space. Third, there is a fundamental difference in the types of space. The space of sedentary societies is marked by borders, walls, and roads. Nomads, however, live in “smooth” space, where reference points shift with their movement – like sand dunes shifting in the desert, accompanied by a barely perceptible sound. The nomad claims this mobile, smooth space as their own – this is their mode of dwelling and their principle of territoriality (Deleuze J., Guattari F. 1992: 186). It is not difficult to observe that the interpretation of nomadism and nomadic space by these authors is speculative, highly abstract, and does not correspond to actual reality. It must be stated immediately that Deleuze and Guattari are not interested in the lived reality of nomadic life. In their “nomadology,” they deal only with an imagined nomadism, and their treatise is merely one of many works aimed against structuralist discourse.

The vast territory of what is now Kazakhstan is heterogeneous. It lies at the intersection of various geographical zones and, even after the onset of aridization, has been and still is characterized by diverse geographic and climatic conditions. As Kazakh philosopher T. Gabitov explains, the predominance of the nomadic type of life on the territory of Kazakhstan until the early 20th century was due to the fact that the nomadic economic and cultural model was able to make optimal use of the climatic and landscape features of Kazakhstan. “This can be referred to as the ‘rotation of seasonal pastures’, and it demonstrates that the forest-steppes of Northern Kazakhstan, where precipitation is abundant and sufficient fodder for livestock is available, the alpine meadows of mountain regions, river valleys, and lakes were used by Kazakhs as *zhailau* (summer pastures). The southern and central regions, where there is little snow in winter and conditions are favorable for *tebenevka* (winter grazing), were selected as wintering areas. Spring and autumn pastures were located adjacent to the wintering sites of livestock” (Gabitov 2004: 296). The ancestors of the Kazakhs, like other peoples who were forced to adopt a nomadic way of life, provided a worthy response to the challenge of Nature. They not only had to transform their economic practices but also their social organization, developing new customs and traditions, a new worldview, and a new way of relating to the world (Shurshitbay, Kabdrakhmanova, Seitembetov, Zhirenova 2023). A vast portion of Kazakhstan is covered by steppe, but there are also mountainous areas and fertile lands. The latter are predominantly located in the present-day regions of Southern Kazakhstan and Semirechye (*Zhetysu*). The region of Semirechye lies at the intersection of agricultural oases and nomadic steppe. This geographic position largely determined the character and specific features of cultural formation and development in this area. Culture in this region developed and functioned as a unique synthesis of agriculture and animal husbandry. Farmers and herders were not antagonistic toward each other; on the contrary, they cooperated and adopted certain customs, habits, and skills from one another. According to K. M. Baipakov, the closest interaction between nomads and sedentary populations in this area occurred from the second half of the 9th century to the beginning of the 13th century. During this period, pastoralism was combined with agriculture. The population of this region led a semi-nomadic, semi-sedentary way of life. A similar situation existed in Eastern Kazakhstan. For this reason, cities have existed in the Semirechye region since ancient times. The most well-known among them is *Otrar* (for more on this city, see (Baipakov K. M., L. Erzakovich. B. 1971). The name *Otrar* appears in written sources at the beginning of the 9th century and is mentioned as a major city. Caliph al-Ma'mun decided to impose tribute upon it. K. M. Baipakov and L. B. Erzakovich further write: “As early as the 10th century, the city of Shavgar is mentioned halfway between *Otrar* and *Sauran*. Judging by this account, *Shavgar* was located in the area of present-day Turkestan. The city was known by this name until the 12th century, when a new name *Yasy* came into use. From the mid-16th century, *Yasy* belonged to the Kazakhs, and it was at that time that a new name Turkestan appeared. The Kazakh khans made it their center, and, apparently seeking to emphasize the city's importance within the Turkestan region, they named it Turkestan. Until the end of the 18th century (with some interruptions), it remained the largest center and official residence of the Kazakh khans of both the Senior and Middle *zhuz*” (Baipakov K. M., L. Erzakovich. B. 1971:140-142). As early as the 9th century, Sayram was known as a fortified settlement in the Turkestan region. There also existed a large city of the same name. It is particularly famous for being the birthplace of the Sufi thinker Khoja Ahmed Yasawi. In the “Treatise and Sayram” it is stated: “Sayram has three names: one of them is Madinat al-Bayda, another is Isfidjab, and the third is Sayram” Referring to the works of Mahmud al-Kashgari, V. Bartold argued that the “White City” – Isfidjab – and Sayram were the same place (Baipakov K. M., L. Erzakovich. B. 1971: 467).

The nomadic way of life created a distinctive and original culture, in many respects opposite to that of sedentary peoples. Therefore, it is methodologically and philosophically inadmissible to apply the measures of one culture to another. Nevertheless, Western academic disciplines as history, cultural studies, etc. have often uncritically assessed the cultures of nomadic peoples based on the criteria of sedentary civilizations. It was precisely from this position that Arnold J. Toynbee viewed nomadic societies and their cultures as retarded in their development. This perspective on Kazakh nomadic culture was also held by the government of the Russian Empire.

The differences between sedentary and nomadic cultures are most clearly visible at the level of spatial organization. Cultural space is just as “beyond nature” as any other cultural phenomenon. While it has natural “anchors,” it simultaneously exists in another dimension. Like everything in culture, space possesses both real and ideal, value-semantic levels. The key distinction by which nomadic and sedentary cultures can be compared is the method of spatial organization, its structural principle.

The space of sedentary culture, regardless of its level of development, is organized according to the principle of “center-periphery” in the horizontal dimension and “top-bottom” in the vertical. At the same time, its horizontal structure is endowed with the greatest positive significance, which diminishes the further one moves toward the periphery. Conversely, significance increases when moving from the margins toward the center. In the secular (profane) context, for example, the capital is considered the main point of attraction within the state, while other cities and especially villages represent the periphery. Within this structure, the city acts as a center in relation to the village. A similar hierarchy is observed in the sacred (religious) dimension.

By contrast, the worldview and existential experience of nomads is deeply intertwined with an awareness of the interrelation between the human world and the natural world. In nomadic culture, unlike in sedentary culture, the unity of material and spiritual principles is expressed more closely, more extensively, and more inseparably. The domain of material culture among nomads is less differentiated, while in sedentary civilizations this differentiation increases historically with cultural progress.

In the collective monograph *The Kazakhs: A Historical and Ethnographic Study*, there is a chapter titled “Domestic Trades and Crafts” (Mukanov 1995). A wide range of activities is analyzed. The author highlights such types as “Woodworking Art”, “Jewelry Art”, “Bone Carving Art” among others. In addition, he identifies “Raw Materials” and “Domestic Trades”, which include the production of household items such as felt-making, mat-weaving, and embroidery, typically done by women. While the collection of raw materials, weaving of mats, and so on can be considered material activity, even though this is not absolute, jewelry and bone-carving arts, along with their products, cannot be attributed solely to the material sphere. Therefore, when considering the relationship between the material and spiritual elements in cultural artifacts, a more nuanced approach is required. An even more refined embodiment of the material-

utilitarian and spiritual principles is found in the nomadic dwelling (the portable, collapsible yurt). The yurt, the traditional dwelling of Kazakhs during migration, was so perfected by the Kazakhs that it belongs not so much to material culture as to spiritual culture, being more imbued with spiritual content than any other phenomenon of nomadic life. Every element of its structure carries semiotic connotations: each part has symbolic meaning and cosmic correspondence, such that the yurt appears both as a dwelling and as a model of the universe. Its structure is as follows: “The framework of the yurt consists of three parts: *kerege* (the lattice wall), *uyk* (ribs supporting the upper dome), and *shanyrak* (the central circular ring at the top), each corresponding to a vertical level. In turn, the felt covering also consists of three parts: *tuyrlyk* (covering the lattice base), *uzuk* (covering the dome ribs), and *tundik* (the felt piece that covers the top ring). Thus, the roof material also forms three levels” (Margulan 1997:166). The *kerege*, *uyk*, and *shanyrak*, when vertically connected by the central pole (*bakan*), symbolize the World Tree. Each of these components has cosmic associations, positioning the yurt as both dwelling and cosmos. Additionally, the yurt and its components are symbolically related to parts of the human body. This describes the vertical structure of the yurt. However, as A. Toleubaev notes, “in horizontal planning, the Kazakh yurt has seven clearly demarcated zones, each of which carries specific functional and symbolic meaning, and reflects the religious-mythological worldview of its creators” (Margulan 1997: 168). The *shanyrak* is the most sacralized element of the yurt. On one hand, it marks the boundary between top and bottom, and on the other, between the inner and outer worlds. “Through the *shanyrak*, the inhabitants of the yurt are connected to the sacred celestial bodies: the sun, moon, and stars. The entrance of daylight, of sunbeams into the dwelling through the *shanyrak*, was given special importance by Kazakhs” (Margulan 1997: 169). Another crucial part of the yurt, with ritual and sacred significance, as noted by A. Toleubaev, is the hearth. Kazakhs referred to it as *kindik* (“navel,” or “the navel of the yurt”) (Margulan 1997: 170). All of these sacred symbols have been revived and popularized in the contemporary history of independent Kazakhstan.

As for the sphere of culture, which must begin with religion, as from ancient times the central element of every people’s culture was religion. The first form of religion among the population stretching from Western Kazakhstan to Western China was Tengrism. It was simultaneously a religion and a worldview. “The fundamental and key category for understanding Tengrism is Tengri. In ancient Turkic inscriptions and in Mahmud al-Kashgari’s *Divan Lughat at-Turk*, the word Tengri is written as *Тәңри* (Таңри). Across different cultural traditions, while preserving its core meaning, it is spelled and pronounced differently: among the Altai peoples – *Тенри*, among the Yakuts – *Таңра*, among the Mongols – *Тәңер*, among the Buryats – *Төңери*. In several modern Turkic languages (including Kazakh), it is pronounced and written as *Tanir*. The word Tengri is Proto-Turkic in origin and later entered the Hunnic language. It consists of two roots – *Tәң* and *ri*: the first means ‘Sky,’ the second means ‘Human.’ In modern Turkic languages, the word *er* (*ir*) means ‘man’” (Ayupov 2012: 18–19). However, in the worldview of ancient China, the Sky (Tian) was also regarded as the supreme deity.

Researchers note that alongside Tengrism, Kazakhs and other Turkic peoples also practiced shamanism. Shamanism is difficult to classify strictly as a religion. Some scholars regard it as an ancient mystical practice, distinct from other forms of early primitive religiosity. M. Orynbeckov writes: “Shamanism emerged from within Tengrism, whose foundations were the Upper, Middle, and Lower worlds; shamans served as mediators who established universal connections between humans, the worlds, and the spirits that governed them. The goal of shamanism was to establish communication with the spirits inhabiting the Middle world” (Orynbeckov 2013: 25). At a certain stage in the development of nomadic society, Tengrism faded from the historical stage, while shamanism continued to exist. This is explained by the fact that its central figure the shaman is a highly unique character. “Shamans”, wrote Sh. Ualikhanov, “were revered as people protected by the heavens and spirits. A shaman is a person endowed with magic and knowledge, superior to others; he is a poet, a musician, a seer, and at the same time a healer” (Valikhanov 1985: 52).

In later times, Kazakhs came under the influence of Mithraism, Zoroastrianism, Buddhism, Manichaeism, as well as Christianity in the forms of Nestorianism and Jacobitism. However, all of these were eventually displaced by Islam of the Sunni branch, specifically of the Hanafi school. V. Bartold wrote: “By the 14th century, Islam had become the state religion throughout the territories conquered by the Mongols from Southern Russia to the borders of Mongolia and China” (Barthold 2002: 213). Nevertheless, Sh. Ualikhanov observed: “Islam has not yet entered into our flesh and blood. In our steppe, we are in a period of dual faith...” (Valikhanov 1985: 71). He explained that among an illiterate people without mullahs, Islam could not take root, remaining instead a sound, a phrase, under which previous shamanistic concepts were concealed. As a result, names and words changed, but the core ideas remained shamanic. The *ongon* came to be called *aruakh*, *kotengri* – Allah or *Khudai*, the spirit of the earth — *shaitan*, *peri*, *diuana*, and *jinn*, but the underlying idea remained rooted in shamanism. Even in their representations, these spirits retained shamanic imagery. Nevertheless, the foundations of shamanic belief were shaken by Islamic monotheism (Valikhanov Ch. Ch. 1985: 49). The northern route of the famous Silk Way passed through the Kazakh steppe. This was, in the words of M. Bakhtin, a unique chronotope. Along this route, diverse peoples, both nomadic and sedentary, encountered one another, exchanging not only goods but also customs, beliefs, and worldviews. Over time, however, the significance of this chronotope diminished. N. Kerimova and Zh. Tulibayeva write: “The development of maritime navigation and the Great Geographical Discoveries of the late 15th and early 16th centuries led to the gradual decline of the Silk Way as the greatest transport corridor in human history, which had connected Europe and Asia all the way to the Pacific Ocean. However, the extensive network of caravan routes in Central Asia, once part of the Silk Road system, continued to play an important role in intra-regional trade and connections with neighboring countries even in later times” [29, p. 63]. By the 15th century, the Silk Way had declined.

However, the culture of the Kazakh nomadic world did not fall into desolation. On the contrary, it remained vibrant precisely because a unique spiritual culture had long been established in the steppe – one that could no longer be destroyed. The greatest development was achieved in musical, poetic, and oral traditions. “The principal marker of ancient nomadic culture”, writes D. Kshibekov, “is oral folk creativity” (Krzybekov 1984:183-184). The people themselves composed songs and crafted numerous musical instruments. K. Zhuzbasov lists the following: “*dombra*, *kobyz*, *sybyzgy*, *dauylpaz*, *yskyryk*, *kamys syrnyay*, *kos syrnyay*, *bugyshak*, *muniz syrnyay*, *kerey*, *sherter*, *zhetigen*, *shankhayyz*, *dabyl*, *dangara*, *shyn kepshik*, *asatayak*, *qonyrau*. Among these instruments”, he adds, “some belong to the percussion family (membranophones), others to the wind (aerophones), still others to percussive idiophones, and some to plucked and bowed string instruments (chordophones)” (Zhuzbasov 1995:178). As A. Zataevich notes, “the most beloved and widespread musical instrument among the Kyrgyz [Kazakhs] is the *dombra*...” (Zataevich 2004: 20). Naturally, some instruments were borrowed from neighbors or inherited from ancestors; some were improved upon, and many were created independently by the Kazakhs themselves.

Until the 20th century, all Kazakh artistic creation, whether musical, poetic, or epic, was exclusively folk art. Even in cases where a particular work had a known author, such epic tales as *Koblandy Batyr*, *Alpamys*, *Er Targyn*, *Kyz Zhibek*, and others were clearly the products not of one author, but of multiple generations who shaped and refined them over time. The visual arts of the Kazakhs, as with

other nomadic peoples of the Eurasian steppe, were primarily decorative and applied in nature. A distinctive feature was the so-called Scythian animal style (on this, see: (Kuzembayuly, Abil 2006).

This raises the question: can the peoples who, prior to the Common Era, transitioned from sedentary to nomadic lifestyles on the present territory of Kazakhstan be called Kazakhs? It is difficult to give a definitive answer. It is likely that many peoples bearing various ethnonyms once passed through this territory, taking their names with them when they moved on. It is, however, evident that the majority of these peoples were of *Turkic* origin.

The Historical Formation of Kazakh Identity

According to the prevailing theory, the word “Kazakh” in Old Turkic translates as “free, independent person.” In Islamic written sources, the term appears in an anonymous Turkic-Arabic dictionary, presumably compiled in Egypt and known from a 1245 manuscript published by M. Houtsma in Leiden in 1894, where it is defined as “nomad” or “wanderer.” From the early 16th century, after part of the nomadic tribes from the territory of modern-day Kazakhstan migrated to Mawarannahr under Shaybani Khan, the term Kazakh began to acquire an ethnic meaning (Perevodchikova 1994). In 1960, S. K. Ibragimov, in his article “Once Again on the Term ‘Kazakh’,” wrote: “Since the late 15th century, the term Kazakh gained political significance, being used to denote separate feudal domains established by the descendants of Barak – Janibek, Kerei, and Burunduk; after the migration of part of the nomadic tribes from the modern territory of Kazakhstan to Mawarannahr under Shaybani Khan, the term Kazakh began to take on an ethnic character” (quoted in: (Abusenova M. H. 1985:41) see also: (Blagova 1970). There is also a perspective on the origin of this ethnonym offered by the well-known scholar, academician V. Bartold (see: (Bartold 1963: 270).

The territory of Kazakhstan is geographically and environmentally diverse. A vast portion of the country is steppe, but there are also mountainous regions and fertile lands. The latter are found predominantly in present-day Southern Kazakhstan and Semirechye (Zhetysu). “This region”, notes K. M. Baipakov, “lies at the junction of agricultural oases and nomadic steppe. Such a position has historically determined the unique character of cultural development. Here, in the contact zone between farming and herding, the interactions between farmers and herders, sedentarism and nomadism, city and steppe are most vividly expressed. These interactions were multifaceted – political, economic, cultural, and ethnic” (Bajpakov 1989: 336). According to K. M. Baipakov, the closest interaction between nomads and sedentary populations in this area occurred from the second half of the 9th to the beginning of the 13th century (see: (Bajpakov 1989: 344–345).

Traditional Kazakh society was organized into three major groupings known as *zhuz*. Historians have not yet reached consensus on the origin of the term or the time of their emergence. N. A. Atagaev writes: “*The Senior Zhuz* of the Kazakhs, which traditionally occupied the territory of southeastern Kazakhstan (Zhetysu) and southern Kazakhstan, included the following tribes: Zhalair, Oshakty, Dulat, Suan, Alban, Kanly, Shanyshkaly, Sary-Uysun, Shapyrashty, Syrgeli, and Ysty.

The Middle Zhuz, traditionally inhabiting central, northern, eastern, and part of southern Kazakhstan, was composed of six tribes: Argyns, Naimans, Kipchaks, Kereys, Uaks, and Konyrats.

Western Kazakhstan was traditionally occupied by the Kazakhs of the *Junior Zhuz*, which was subdivided into three major tribal unions: Alimuly, Baiuly, and Zhetiru” (Atygaev 2007:411). While all *zhuz* members were part of a single Kazakh people, each *zhuz* and its constituent tribes maintained specific characteristics that served as the basis for recognizing others and for self-identification. By the 14th or, at the latest, the 15th century, the Kazakh ethnoses had emerged as a cohesive whole, albeit composed of three relatively distinct *zhuzes*. All Kazakhs shared the same ethnic and cultural identity. Kazakhstan was monocultural, as both a territory and a proto-state. However, this was only up to a certain point.

As M. Tynyshpaev notes, “...the history of the formation of the Kazakh Khanate is closely tied to the history of the Golden Horde...” (Tynyshpaev 2009:152). The Golden Horde appeared in the 1230s. In Eastern literature, this state was known as the Ulus of Jochi, while in Russian sources it was called the Golden Horde. “Although,” as A. Yu. Yakubovsky observes, “it remains unclear when and why this latter name arose” (Yakubovsky 1950: 152). Chinggis Khan united the Mongols and, after creating a great army, moved westward, establishing a powerful empire, the Golden Horde, which was divided into right and left wings, and then into *uluses* (Yakubovsky 1950: 367). “By the 1230s,” writes Yakubovsky, “the Mongols had become full masters of the Dasht-i Qipchaq, laying the foundation for a vast and powerful state, known in Eastern literature as the Ulus of Jochi, or the Blue Horde, and in Russian sources as the Golden Horde” (Yakubovsky 1950:35). This means that all tribes and clans inhabiting the territory of the Deshti Kipchak became vassals of the Mongols. K. Daniyarov asserts that the history of the Kazakh people begins with the formation of the Golden Horde, since, according to him, it was “from the Kazakh people that Chinggis Khan emerged, the man who succeeded in uniting the fragmented Kazakh clans living in the territory of present-day Mongolia, leading them out of barren desert lands into the area of modern Kazakhstan, incorporating the remaining Kazakh clans of that territory into his then still small state, and creating a powerful polity that played a significant role in Eurasia for over 300 years” (Данияров 2001: 195). Daniyarov refers to the well-known monument *The Secret History of the Mongols* as the epic Chinggis Khan. He writes: “In my research of the heroic epic Chinggis Khan, written in Old Uyghur script in the Old Kazakh language, found in Beijing and dated to the year 1240, known in Chinese as Yuan Chao Bi Shi (History of the Yuan Dynasty), and by Russian researchers as *The Secret History of the Mongols*, I have established, it may be said irrefutably, that there is no trace of Mongolian or Chinese. The heroic epic Chinggis Khan was written in the Kazakh language of that time and must be classified among the historical and cultural heritage of the Kazakh people” (Daniyarov 2001:442). Objective historical scholarship, of course, does not accept such claims. Chinggis Khan is not a historical figure to whom the genealogy of ethnic groups can be ascribed. As R. K. Kadyrzhanov notes, “the tendencies toward antiquating and glorifying national histories among post-Soviet nations are methodologically based on a primordialist understanding of nation and history” (Kundakbayeva J. (2009: 274).

The Golden Horde was not composed of a single people. It consisted of conquerors who subjugated the peoples of the Dashti Kipchak, as well as the conquered peoples who inhabited that region. Accordingly, a single unified culture could not and did not exist in the Ulus of Jochi. Numerically, the conquerors were inferior to the Turkic population of the Dashti Kipchak. They could not impose Mongolization on the Turks, quite the opposite occurred: the Mongols gradually became Turkified. They adopted the Turkic language. Moreover, as A. Yakubovsky notes, “by the 14th century, a literary language had already formed in the Ulus of Jochi (Golden Horde) — not Mongolian, but Turkic, and it exhibited features of Kipchak and Oghuz elements...” (Kadyrzhanov 2014:66). From the 1360s onward, the empire founded by Chinggis Khan began to disintegrate. Its constituent parts began to acquire *de facto* independence. The process of dissolution

started in the 1420s. Several independent khanates emerged, including the Siberian, Uzbek, and Kazakh Khanates (the latter in 1465). By 1459, the Golden Horde had ceased to exist as a unified state.

K. K. Daniyarov believes that the Kazakh Khanate arose in 1468, following the death of Khan Abulkhair, and became fully independent “only in 1480 after the final dissolution of the Ulus of Jochi – the Golden Horde” (Daniyarov 2001: 73).

M. Tynyshpaev writes that after the collapse of the Golden Horde, various khanates emerged on its ruins, engaging in internecine conflicts for dominance. One such polity was the Uzbek Ulus, whose population, at the time, had no direct relation to the modern Uzbek people. As T. Sultanov notes, “the Uzbek Ulus included, in particular, the territories of present-day Central, Northern, Northeastern, and Western Kazakhstan” (Sultanov 2009: 259). He further writes that after the death of Khan Abulkhair (in 1468/1469), a power struggle ensued within the ulus. Sultans Kerey and Janibek returned to the territory, seized power, and established the Kazakh Khanate. As a result, the Uzbek Ulus disintegrated. Thus, according to T. Sultanov, the Kazakh Khanate was founded “in 875 A.H. / 1470–1471 C.E. by two sultans, Kerey and Janibek, descendants of Orda, the eldest son of Jochi” (Sultanov 2009: 268). “The name Kazakh,” writes Sultanov, “was initially applied to the khanate, and later became the name of the people; from the early decades of the 16th century, the country came to be known as Kazakhstan”.

“Since that time and until today, the indigenous inhabitants of this vast country have referred to themselves as Kazakhs, more precisely as Qazaqs; the original form of this Turkic word is precisely this – with two uvular q sounds: at the beginning and the end – qazaq” (Sultanov 2009: 261). Research shows that regardless of when the Kazakh people proper emerged, the territory of modern Kazakhstan was inhabited since ancient times, from the onset of climatic aridization (and possibly even earlier) by related peoples, presumably Turkic in origin. This is evidenced by the fact that the Kazakhs of the 16th century and beyond differ little from their predecessors in terms of worldview, customs, beliefs (their original faith being Tengrism), and so forth. Though divided into three zhuzes, the Kazakhs constituted a unified ethnic group with, in principle, a common culture and a shared cultural, social, and political-organizational identity. This is the historical context in which the Kazakh Khanate was formed.

The nomadic way of life produced a distinctive and original culture that in many respects was the opposite of sedentary culture. Therefore, from both a methodological and philosophical standpoint, it is inappropriate to apply the standards of one culture to another. Nevertheless, Western scholarship, including history, cultural studies, etc. often assessed the cultures of nomadic peoples uncritically through the lens of sedentary civilizations. It was precisely from this perspective that Arnold J. Toynbee viewed nomadic societies and their cultures as “*arrested*” in their development. A similar perspective on Kazakh nomadic culture was held by the imperial government of Russia. The incorporation of Kazakhstan into Russia was not a single event, but a process that extended over more than a century. As T. Sultanov writes, “The incorporation of Kazakhstan into Russia, which began in the 1730s, for a number of reasons was delayed for many decades and concluded only in the 1860s (Sultanov 2009: 261).

From the time official contacts began between the Kazakh khanates and the Russian administration, foreign systems of economic activity and industrial technologies began to penetrate and be imposed upon the traditional culture of the Steppe. Kazakhstan began to be heavily settled by Russians and other ethnic groups from the Russian Empire. This process accelerated especially during the implementation of Pyotr Stolypin’s agrarian reform, which began in 1906. The gradual displacement of Kazakhs from their ancestral lands was a long-term process, continuing throughout the entire period of Russian colonization and lasting 150 years.

G. Turgaraeva notes: “In 1873, the subjugation of the Khiva Khanate by Russia marked the complete removal of the Kazakhs from the influence of other states and their incorporation into the Russian Empire. The decisive events took place in 1864–1865. The annexation of Kazakhstan to Russia was completed” (Turgaraeva 2016:127).

During this period, transformations occurred in the realm of identity, both among the indigenous Kazakh ethnic group and among the ethnic groups that were voluntarily or forcibly resettled in Kazakhstan.

The tsarist government repeatedly attempted to implement a forced sedentarization policy in the region, i.e., to transition Kazakhs from a nomadic to a settled lifestyle. The renowned philosopher Pavel Florensky wrote that “it was irrational on the part of the imperial government to attempt to convert nomadic peoples to sedentary agriculture, which contradicted the millennia-long habits of these peoples and would not have brought any particular benefit to the state even if successful. A more reasonable course of action would have been a transition to a semi-nomadic lifestyle with an emphasis on pastoral cultures” (Florenskij 1996: 653). The Russian Empire ultimately failed to fully sedentarize the Kazakh population. However, what the tsarist regime could not accomplish was successfully imposed by the Bolshevik regime: in the first decades of Soviet rule, sedentarism was forcibly implemented across the region through coercive measures. Most historians consider the incorporation of Kazakhstan into Russia to have been ultimately a positive development. For example, Soviet historian E. Bekmakanov stated: “The incorporation of Kazakhstan into Russia, in terms of its socio-economic and cultural consequences, had deeply progressive significance” (Bekmakanov 1957:217). A fundamentally different view is held by K. K. Daniyarov. According to him, the period from the 18th to the 20th century was “the most tragic in the entire history of the Kazakh state and people. The author does not distinguish between the colonial and Soviet periods but considers them to be a single colonial era” (Daniyarov 2001: 264).

In our view, the most balanced perspective is expressed by S. Suleymenov and V. Basin: “Russian-Kazakh relations during this period represent a synthesis of oppression and progress, struggle and cooperation. The reactionary stands in opposition to the progressive, the progressive to the reactionary, in an irreconcilable antagonism that finds its resolution during the October Revolution. This is the true objective reality” (Suleymenov and Basin 1981:173). Shokan Ualikhanov became a scholar of international stature. From the second half of the 19th century, written Kazakh literature began to develop, with its brightest representative being Abai (Ibrahim) Kunanbayev. Books in the Kazakh language began to be published. Russian culture exerted a largely positive influence on the development of Kazakh culture. A. Kadyrbayev and Zh. Syzdykova note: “Culture became perhaps the only sphere of public life in Central Asia in which Russian conquest can be characterized as, on the whole, a progressive phenomenon” (Kadyrbaev, Syzdykova 2008: 182). The Russian Empire failed to completely sedentarize the Kazakh population. However, what the imperial authorities could not achieve was realized by the Bolshevik regime: already in the early decades of Soviet rule, sedentarism was imposed throughout the region by all available coercive means. E. Bekmakanov points to another significant negative consequence of Kazakhstan’s incorporation into the Russian Empire: “The new system of governance,” he writes, “led to the intermixing of various Kazakh clans” (Bekmakanov 1957:108). The internal policy of the Russian Empire toward the Kazakh population and other peoples incorporated into its domain from the second half of the 19th century is best described, following D. Vasiliev, as a policy of Russification. This policy was sometimes referred to by the neutral term obrusenie (“Russification”), implying a non-coercive, historically organic “rapprochement with the Russian people, becoming Russian in language

and tradition” (Vasiliev 2008:171). According to Vasiliev, “Russification included political, economic, administrative, legal, cultural, and everyday components. However, education rightfully played the central role” (Vasiliev 2008:172). Kazakhstan’s entry into the USSR further intensified migration flows from across the Soviet Union to its territory. Particularly notable were the deportations of Crimean Tatars, Koreans, and representatives of other nationalities in the years preceding the Great Patriotic War, as well as during the so-called Virgin Lands Campaign (1954–1965).

Violence, repression, and terror became key instruments of Bolshevik rule from the very first days following the October coup. The new government bore the hallmarks of a junta that had usurped power. To maintain its rule, the All-Russian Extraordinary Commission, headed by F. Dzerzhinsky, was established. What kind of political regime was this? Journalists quickly coined the term totalitarian, which became widely accepted. With the establishment of Soviet power in Kazakhstan, certain cultural movements and traditional customs, especially of religious or mythological origin, were classified as “remnants” and targeted for eradication. Moreover, a number of prominent Kazakh cultural figures whose ideas and writings were at odds with the official ideology (A. Bukeikhanov, B. Karatayev, A. Baitursynov, and others) were subject to deliberate suppression. Since Russian was declared the official state language of the USSR, the Kazakh language became marginalized — especially in urban centers of the increasingly multiethnic Kazakhstan. Nevertheless, there were also positive consequences of Kazakhstan’s inclusion in the Soviet Union — notably, the near-total eradication of illiteracy.

The most tragic period, however, one that inflicted immense loss and trauma upon the Kazakh people, was the era of collectivization. The collectivization campaign in Kazakhstan was led by F. I. Goloshchyokin (real name: Shaia Itsikovich), secretary of the Kazakh Regional Committee of the Communist Party (Bolsheviks). He orchestrated what amounted to a genocide of the Kazakh population. In party circles, Goloshchyokin was known for his arrogance, demagoguery, and cynicism. He did not consider Kazakhs to be full-fledged people. No sooner had he arrived in Kazakhstan than he declared that Soviet power was absent and that a “Small October” was needed (Aden A. (2019). He even tried to arrange Kazakh yurts as if they were village houses lined along streets. Whatever vague boundaries between zhuzes and clans had survived into the 19th century disappeared. All Kazakhs were forcibly transitioned to a sedentary lifestyle. The indigenous population became intermixed with settlers who flooded into Kazakhstan. Prior to its incorporation into the Russian Empire, the Kazakhs were a monoethnic people. When newcomers (primarily Russians and Ukrainians) began arriving, especially during the Stolypin reforms, the issue of ethnic identity came to the fore. The newcomers differed not only in appearance, but also in lifestyle, values, customs, religion, in short, culture. The Kazakhs did not experience a full-blown identity crisis, but they did become increasingly aware of their own distinctiveness. Under Soviet conditions, ethnic and cultural identity became even more sharply defined.

The situation began to stabilize somewhat from the early 1930s, in the sense that the Soviet Union was not yet under imminent threat of war. However, in 1932–1933, Kazakhstan was struck by the Great Famine (*Dzhut*) (Михайлов 1996). Following collectivization, a new wave of hardship descended upon the long-suffering people in the form of industrialization (Lelchuk, Ilyin, Kosheleva 1989). At the same time, the country was swept up in mass political repressions. All leaders of the Alash Orda movement were executed (Alash is a Horde. (2009). “Representatives of Kazakh literature, such as S. Seifullin, B. Mailin, I. Zhansugurov, M. Zhumabayev, and M. Dulatov, were repressed and executed. A serious blow was dealt to Kazakh science. Repressions targeted the founder of Kazakh linguistics A. Baitursynov, renowned linguist Professor K. Zhubanov, founder of the Kazakh historical school Professor S. D. Asfendiyarov, one of the heads of the Kazakh branch of the USSR Academy of Sciences M. Tulepov, and others” (Kozybaev, Nurpeis, Zhukeshev 2011: 84).

B. G. Ayagin and his co-authors rightly point out: “Soviet socialism was indeed two-faced. Alongside the enormous destructive power carried by Bolshevism: the collapse of the former state, the destruction of traditional culture, the mass killing of citizens, the demolition of churches, mosques, and synagogues. It also, beginning in the 1930s, built schools, opened universities, developed socialist national culture, and constructed roads and hydroelectric plants across the country” (Ayagan, Abzhanov, Seliverstov, Bekenova 2010:109). These contradictory forces were inextricably linked. Nominally, Soviet power supported national cultures and seemingly did not oppress them. Moreover, it introduced written languages for ethnic groups that previously had none. The development of native languages was encouraged, and education in these languages was conducted at the secondary school level. However, higher education in the republics was often conducted in Russian, the official state language. Thus, informally and perhaps not always intentionally, the practice of Russification was carried out across the country. While people in rural areas continued to speak their native languages, in cities, especially large ones, the indigenous population often used Russian even in everyday life. Attempts to correct this situation generally led to no substantial change.

At the end of 1991, the Soviet Union ceased to exist. The former Soviet republics, including Kazakhstan, became independent states. The finest elements of traditional Kazakh culture began to re-emerge. The Kazakh language was elevated to the status of the state language, and religion was rehabilitated. Today, Kazakhstan and its culture are experiencing a new stage of development, especially after overcoming the tendency toward a super-presidential regime. However, this does not mean that all conditions for further progress are already in place. In recent decades, the world has entered a state of turbulence. The struggle between the forces of globalization and those of monocentric globalism (Hamidov 2005). has intensified, and its outcome remains uncertain. Nevertheless, there is hope that the former, a more pluralistic and inclusive globalization, will prevail.

Conclusion

Analysis has shown that, regardless of the precise moment when the Kazakh people proper emerged, the territory of modern-day Kazakhstan has been inhabited since ancient times, at least since the period of climatic aridization (and possibly even earlier), by related peoples, presumably of Turkic origin. This is evidenced by the fact that the Kazakhs of the 16th century and later differ only slightly from their predecessors in terms of worldview, customs, beliefs (Tengrism being the original faith), and other aspects. Although historically divided into three zhuzes, the Kazakhs constituted a single ethnic group, with a fundamentally unified culture and a shared cultural, social, and political-organizational identity. Since Kazakhstan’s incorporation into the Russian Empire and later into the Soviet Union, identification processes (including cultural identification) on its territory have become increasingly disordered and complex. Upon gaining state independence, Kazakhstan inherited the ethno-cultural situation that had formed by the time of the USSR’s collapse. Based on this legacy, the country is now compelled to construct a unified, humanistically oriented ethno-national and ethno-cultural policy.

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Words:

Characters: 11381 (10,5 standard page)

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